

The Fat and the Oil from the Seeds of *Actinodaphne Hookeri*, Meissn. An Indigenous Source of Lauric Acid.

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During the investigation on the alkaloid from the bark of *Actinodaphne* (Krishna and Ghose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 429) the seeds were examined for their alkaloidal content. No alkaloid, however, was found in them but only a small quantity (1%) of an essential oil which appeared in its characteristics to be similar to the oil of *Litsæa zeylanica* (Rao, *J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1932, 15A, 72) which like *Actinodaphne Hookeri* belongs to the N. O. Laurinacea. Apart from the essential oil, the seeds contained a large quantity of a fat and an oil which has been described by Kirtikar and Basu ("Indian Medicinal Plants," Pt. II, p. 1103) as 'Pisitela' employed medicinally as an external application to sprains. Of the species of the N. O. Laurinacea occurring in India, only the fats from the seeds of *Litsæa sebifera* and *L. zeylanica* appear to have been studied (Schroeder, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1905, 243, 631; Hooper, *Annual Report, Indian Museum*, 1910, p. 10) and in order to collect additional information it was thought desirable to investigate the composition of the fat from *Actinodaphne Hookeri*.

The results obtained show that the kernels contain a fat which consists mainly of trilaurin (96%) and endocarp contains an oil which consists mainly of the glycerides of oleic acid but the fat as extracted is never obtained in pure form and is always found to contain small quantities of triolein. In actual practice, it is not possible to separate the seed-shells (endocarp) from the kernels or the kernels from the endocarp very completely with the result that some of the oil from the endocarp gets mixed with the fat and *vice versa*. The fat, which is hard and slightly coloured, can very easily be purified, a single crystallisation from alcohol giving pure trilaurin of iodine value 1.

Not many examples are known where a fat from natural sources has been found to consist of a glyceride of a single fatty acid and, therefore, the investigation is of further interest from an academic point of view. It has also a commercial interest in that the fat could be employed as an indigenous source of lauric acid.

The Kernel Fat.

The *actinodaphne* seeds used in this investigation were obtained from Mahableshwar (Bombay Presidency). The kernels were separated from the endocarp, powdered and extracted with petroleum ether when contain 75% of a fat (or 48.4% of the original seeds) was obtained. For determination of the physical and chemical constants, the powdered kernels were expressed at about 50° in a hydraulic press and in this manner only 48% (or 31% of the seeds) of a pale yellow oil was obtained which on standing became hard and crystalline.

General characteristics.

Consistency	Hard, brittle and crystalline
Colour	Pale yellow
M.p.	43-4°
Sp. gr.	0.925 at 25°
Refractive index	1.4490 at 30°
Saponification value	255.5
Iodine value (Hanus)	10.9
Acetyl value	11.3
Hehner value	91.0
Acid value	4.0
Unsaponifiable matter	1.92%

Composition of the fatty acids.—The fat, when crystallised from a large volume of alcohol, was obtained in fine silky needles, m.p. 45-46°, saponification value 264, and iodine value 1.2. The fat when saponified gave an acid which on crystallisation from dilute alcohol melted at 43-44° and had M.W. 200.5. Its melting point when mixed with an authentic sample of lauric acid remained unchanged. These facts indicated that the fat was almost entirely trilaurin.

For the determination of the composition of the fat, as much as possible of the sparingly soluble trilaurin of iodine value 0, was removed by crystallisation of the fat from 95% alcohol and the residue left in the mother liquor was then saponified and separated into solid and liquid acids by the Twitchell's method. Identification of the acids was conducted as described later.

Chemical constants of the mixed fatty acids.

Mean molecular weight	202
Iodine value (Hanus)	3.15
Saturated acids	96%
Unsaturated acids	4%

Unsaturated acids.—100 G. of the fat were crystallised from boiling 95 % alcohol (1 litre) and in this way a snow white, silky, needle shaped crystalline product (90 g.) of m.p. 45–46° and saponification value 264, was obtained which was identified as trilaurin. The residual 10 g. of the fat remaining in the mother liquor was saponified with alcoholic potash and the acids liberated. The fatty acids (9.5 g.) thus isolated were further separated into solid and liquid acids by the lead salt—alcohol method and in this manner the following two fractions were obtained: Fraction A—liquid acids (5.8 g.) of iodine value 61.7, and Fraction B—solid acids (3.7 g.) of iodine value 3.2.

A portion of the liquid acids on bromination did not yield any hexabromide nor could any tetrabromide be isolated from the brominated product. Another portion of (A) was converted into its potassium soap and oxidised in the cold by a dilute solution of potassium permanganate according to the method of Lapworth and Mottram (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1628). The oxidised product, after removal of the unoxidised portion with petroleum ether and after being twice crystallised from alcohol, melted at 129.30° and had a M. W. of 318 and was identified as dihydroxystearic acid. The unoxidised portion was left as a pasty brown mass which on washing with dilute alcohol and drying was found to have a M. W. of 210. These experiments indicated that the unsaturated acids in the portion (A) consisted mainly of oleic acid and that the acids of more than one double bond, namely, linoleic and linolenic etc., were absent. They also indicated that portions (A) and (B) still contained some solid acid most of which was lauric. The amount of liquid acids being small, their conversion into methyl esters and subsequent fractionation was not attempted.

Saturated acids.—The solid acids (B), on twice crystallisation from dilute alcohol, melted at 43.44° and had M. W. of 200.5. Its melting point showed no depression when mixed with an authentic sample of pure lauric acid. The fatty acids, (B), therefore, consisted mainly of lauric acid with a little oleic acid as indicated by their iodine value.

In order to prepare the methyl ester 325 g. of the mixed acids, from which the unsaponifiable matter had been removed, was successively crystallised from 75 % alcohol to remove oleic acid as completely as possible, and 154 g. of an acid (m. p. 44°; M. W. 200.7 and iodine value 1.5) was isolated. This was converted into its

methyl ester which distilled at 132-35°/7 mm. and only a small portion (iodine value 4) distilled at 135-160° and this appeared to be a mixture of lauric and oleic esters. The fraction boiling at 132-35° had a saponification equivalent of 214 and the acid liberated from this melted at 43-44° and was identified as lauric acid. The above data on calculation gave the following percentage composition for the mixed acids namely, lauric (96 %) and oleic (4 %).

The Endocarp Oil.

The seed-shells on extraction with petroleum ether gave 25% (8.75 % of the seeds) of a reddish brown oil which on cooling to 20° deposited a solid crystalline matter, subsequently identified as trilaurin. The oil on removal of the solvent and the solid matter was cooled to 0° and filtered rapidly under suction, when a further quantity of trilaurin was removed. The filtrate was used for determining the general characteristics which are as given below.

Consistency	Liquid
Colour	Reddish brown
Sp. gr.	0.9163 at 20°
Refractive index	1.4550 at 25°
Saponification value	199.6
Iodine value (Hanus)	54.6
Acetyl value	77.0
Acid value	100.2
Hebner value	93.0
Unsaponifiable matter	3.56 %

50.5 G. of the oil was saponified in the usual manner and extracted with ether to remove the unsaponifiable matter after which the mixed acids gave the following chemical constants.

Mean molecular weight	265
Iodine value (Hanus)	54.8
Resin acids	11.2%
Saturated fatty acids	33.0%
Unsaturated fatty acids	55.8%

36 G. of the acids from which the unsaponifiable matter had been removed was subjected to the usual Twitchell's separation with the following results.

A—Acids whose lead salts were insoluble in boiling 95% alcohol in the presence of acetic acid (mostly resin acids)	4.08 g.
B—Saturated fatty acids	2.42 g.
C—Unsaturated fatty acids	29.50 g.
				Total	36.00

The acids (A) (M. W. 319; iodine value 18), consisted mainly of resin acid and no definite product could be isolated by crystallisation.

The acids (B) (M.W. 243; iodine value 3·2), on being dissolved in petroleum ether deposited a small amount of resinous matter. The residues from the ethereal filtrate on crystallisation from acetone melted at 48° and had a M. W. of 249. The residue from this on crystallisation from alcohol gave a substance (m.p 44-45° ; M. W. 208). The acids (B), therefore, appear to be a mixture of resin and lauric acids.

The acids (C) (M. W. 268 and iodine value 51·5) were converted into their methyl esters in the usual manner and 28·4 g. of the neutral esters distilled at 2—3/mm. with the following results.

Fraction	B.p.	Weight.	Iodine value.	Component of the esters.		
				Methyl laurate.	Methyl oleate or isomers.	Isomeric methyl dihydroxystearate.
L ₁	107-12°	1·95 g.	4·6	1·85	0·10 g.	
L ₂	112-17°	6·08	8·7	5·46	0·62	
L ₃	132-65°	1·57	31·7	0·99	0·58	
L ₄	165-70°	3·48	68·5	0·70	2·78	
L ₅	170-75°	9·20	81·0	0·00	9·20	
L ₆	175-200°	3·23	58·8		2·21	1·02 g.
Residue		2·70	41·3		1·30	1·40
Loss		0·19	...			
Total		28·40	...	9·00	16·79	2·42

Fractions L₁ and L₂ were mostly methyl laurate, saponification value 213·7 (saponification value for pure methyl laurate being 214) and the liberated acid from the product of saponification was identified as lauric acid. The presence of a little methyl oleate was indicated from its low iodine value.

Fractions L₃ and L₄ appeared to be mixtures of methyl oleate and methyl laurate.

Fraction L₅ was almost entirely methyl oleate, saponification value 300 (pure methyl oleate has a saponification value of 296 and iodine value 85·8).

Fraction L₆ on standing deposited some solid matter (m.p. 65°) which appeared to be the methyl ester of isomeric dihydroxystearic acid (*cf.* Puntambekar and Krishna, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 209).*

* In this paper (pp. 203-212) the following changes are to be read: Isomeric oleic acid for elaidic (isooleic) methyl oleate and isomers for methyl elaidale and oleate. Insert (isomeric) before dihydroxystearic acid (in the heading of the last column of the table, p. 210). The value 1·16% (p. 211, last column of the table) works out to be 2·36%, if instead of myristic acid the presence of palmitic acid is assumed.

The residue was a dark brown viscous mass and appeared to be a mixture of methyl oleate and isomeric methyl dihydroxystearate and the decomposition products.

The above data on calculation gave the following percentage composition for the mixed acids. The mean molecular weight of the resin acids has been taken as 346 (Twitchell, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.* 1891, 10, 805).

Acids.	Weight.	Per cent.
Resin	4.03 g.	11.20
Lauric	11.88	33.00
Oleic and its isomers	17.56	48.78
Isomeric dihydroxystearic	2.53	7.02
Total	<u>36.00</u>	<u>100.00</u>

Unsaponifiable matter from the fat and the oil.—The unsaponifiable matter from the fat was dissolved in hot alcohol and the solution allowed to cool. A flocculent amorphous matter separated out, which on drying melted at 60-70° and appeared to be wax. After removal of this substance the alcoholic solution yielded a phytosterol which after three crystallisations from alcohol melted at 130-31°. Its acetyl derivative melted at 118-19°. This shows that the sterol is sitosterol commonly found in vegetable oils and fats.

The amount of the unsaponifiable matter from the endocarp oil being small in quantity was not investigated further. In appearance and consistency it appeared very much like the unsaponifiable matter from the kernel fat.

SUMMARY.

1. The fat and the oil from the seeds of *Actinodaphne hookeri* are found to contain the glycerides of lauric, oleic, isomeric oleic acids together with sitosterol.
2. The oil contains a small amount of resin acids.
3. The fat appears to be a convenient source for lauric acid.